

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ONE OF BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM FOR THE THIRD-ORDER EQUATION WITH MULTIPLE CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

The article constructs a unique solution to a tertiary-order equation with multiple characteristics with boundary conditions that include all possible local boundary conditions. The uniqueness of the solution of boundary value problems is proved by the method of integral equations using the sign-definiteness of quadratic forms. When proving the existence of a solution to the problem, the Green's function method, the theory of integral equations and potentials are used.

Keywords: Boundary value problems, third order equation, multiple characteristics, quadratic forms, uniqueness of solution, existence of solution, Green's function, potential theory, fundamental solution.

Introduction. In recent years, the desire for mathematical justification of natural phenomena is connected with the study of their mathematical models. For example, the compilation of mathematical models of wave propagation with large amplitudes, tsunami propagation in the oceans, nonlinear wave propagation in shallow waters, hydro-magnetic wave propagation in

cold plasma and acoustic waves in anharmonic crystals is connected with linear and nonlinear equations of odd order ([1]-[6]). Therefore, the study of an odd-order equation with different boundary conditions is one of the urgent problems.

One of such representatives of such equations is the equation

$$Lu \equiv \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^3} - \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

It is known that the fundamental solutions of Eq. (1) have the following form [7]

$$U(x - \xi; t - \tau) = |t - \tau|^{1/3} f\left(\frac{x - \xi}{|t - \tau|^{2/3}}\right), \quad x \neq \xi, t \neq \tau; \quad (2)$$

$$V(x - \xi; t - \tau) = |t - \tau|^{1/3} \varphi\left(\frac{x - \xi}{|t - \tau|^{2/3}}\right), \quad x < \xi, t \neq \tau. \quad (3)$$

Here

$$f(z) = \frac{2}{3}|z|^{1/2} \int_z^\infty \eta^{-3/2} f^*(\eta) d\eta + c^+, \quad z > 0,$$

$$f(z) = \frac{2}{3}|z|^{1/2} \int_{-\infty}^z \eta^{-3/2} f^*(\eta) d\eta + c^-, \quad z < 0,$$

$$\varphi(z) = \frac{2}{3}|z|^{1/2} \int_{-\infty}^z \eta^{-3/2} \varphi^*(\eta) d\eta + c, \quad z < 0,$$

$$f^*(z) = \int_0^\infty \exp\left(-\frac{\lambda^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2}} + \lambda z\right) d\lambda, \quad -\infty < z < \infty,$$

$$\varphi^*(z) = \int_0^\infty \exp(\lambda z - \lambda^{3/2}) dz + \int_0^\infty \exp\left(-\frac{\lambda^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\lambda^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2}} + \lambda z\right) d\lambda, \quad z < 0,$$

$$z = (x - \xi)|t - \tau|^{-2/3}.$$

For function $f(z), \varphi(z), f^*(z), \varphi^*(z)$ fair relation

$$f''(z) + \frac{2}{3}zf^*(z) = 0, \varphi'''(z) + \frac{2}{3}z\varphi^*(z) = 0,$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f^*(z) = \pi, \int_{-\infty}^0 f^*(z) = \frac{2\pi}{3}, \int_0^{\infty} f^*(z) = \frac{\pi}{3}, \int_{-\infty}^0 \varphi^*(z) = 0.$$

In domain $\Omega = \{(x, t) : 0 < x < 1, 0 < t < T\}$ consider equation (1) with the boundary condition:

$$u(x, 0) = \lambda u(x, T), u_t(x, 0) = \mu u_t(x, T), \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha_1(t)u(1, t) + \alpha_2(t)u_{xx}(1, t) = \varphi_1(t), u_x(1, t) = \varphi_2(t), \quad (5)$$

$$\beta_1(t)u(0, t) + \beta_2(t)u_x(0, t) + \beta_3(t)u_{xx}(0, t) = \varphi_3(t). \quad (6)$$

We note that we considered similar problems in [8], [9] only for third-order equations of a different form.

Theorem 1. Let the following conditions be satisfied

$$\lambda\mu = 1, \alpha_2 \neq 0, \beta_3 \neq 0, 2\beta_1\beta_3 - \beta_2^2 \geq 0, \frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2} \leq 0.$$

Then problem (1), (4) does not have more than one solution in the class $u \in C_{x,t}^{3,2}(\Omega) \cap C_{x,t}^{2,1}(\bar{\Omega})$

Let problem (1), (4)-(6) have two solutions $u_1(x, t)$, $u_2(x, t)$. Then assuming $v(x, t) = u_1(x, t) - u_2(x, t)$ we obtain the following homogeneous problem with respect to the function $v(x, t)$.

$$Lv \equiv \frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x^3} - \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad (x, t) \in \Omega,$$

$$\alpha_1(t)v(1, t) + \alpha_2(t)v_{xx}(1, t) = 0, \quad v_x(1, t) = 0,$$

$$\beta_1(t)v(0, t) + \beta_2(t)v_x(0, t) + \beta_3(t)v_{xx}(0, t) = 0.$$

Consider the identity

$$\int_0^1 \int_0^T L(v)v dx dt = 0$$

Consider the identity

$$\int_0^1 \int_0^T v_t^2(x, t) dx dt - \int_0^T \left(\frac{\beta_1}{\beta_3} v^2(0, t) + \frac{\beta_2}{\beta_3} v_x(0, t)v(0, t) - \frac{\alpha_1(t)}{\alpha_2(t)} v^2(1, t) + \frac{1}{2} v_x^2(0, t) \right) dt -$$

$$- (1 - \lambda\mu) \int_0^1 v_t(x, T)v(x, T) dx = 0$$

Hence, by virtue of the conditions of the theorem, the quadratic form

$$Q(t) \equiv \frac{\beta_1}{\beta_3} v^2(1, t) + \frac{\beta_2}{\beta_3} v_x(1, t)v(1, t) + \frac{1}{2} v_x^2(1, t)$$

will be positive definite, i.e. quadratic form $Q(t)$ can be written in the following form:

$$\frac{\beta_1}{\beta_3} v^2(1, t) + \frac{\beta_2}{\beta_3} v_x(1, t)v(1, t) + \frac{1}{2} v_x^2(1, t) = \lambda_1 v_x^2 + \lambda_2 v^2, \quad \lambda_1 > 0, \quad \lambda_2 > 0.$$

Here λ_1 and λ_2 – roots of the characteristic polynomial of a matrix of a quadratic form Q . Then, by virtue of the conditions of the theorem we have $v(x, t) = 0$ in Ω , and due to the continuity of the function $v(x, t)$ in $\bar{\Omega}$ we get that $v(x, t) = 0$ in $\bar{\Omega}$.

The proof of the existence theorem, the solution of problem (1), (4)-(6) is carried out by the Green's function method.

Theorem 2. Let the conditions of Theorem 1 be satisfied and the following conditions

$$\psi_1(x), \psi_2(x) \in C^1([0, 1]); \varphi_1(t) \in C^1([0, T]); \varphi_2(t), \varphi_3(t) \in C([0, T])$$

Then problem (1) (4),-(6) has a unique solution in class $u \in C_{x,t}^{3,2}(\Omega) \cap C_{x,t}^{2,1}(\bar{\Omega})$.

The proof of Theorem 2, i.e. the existence theorem, the solution of problem (1), (4)-(6) is carried out by the Green's function method using the theory of potentials of fundamental solutions of equation (1) and on the basis of the theory of the system of Fredholm integral equations of the second kind.

Conclusions. Based on the research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

– In the proposed method for studying boundary value problems, we will apply all possible local boundary value problems for equations (1), since the boundary condition (5), (6) includes all possible boundary conditions;

– based on the results of this work, one can study the asymptotic properties of solutions to equation (1) in the neighborhood of infinitely distant points of the boundary and irregular points of the boundary;

– Based on the results of this work, it is now possible to construct a solution to boundary value problems in unbounded domains.

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